

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abdul Saman p.i** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABHILASH** of **II BCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ASHWATHI-T** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Ashwin k** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Joyal Dsilva** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Meghana U** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms mohammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mokshith** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms NIHAL ISMAIL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Omkaradithya** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sreelakshmi.A** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sudarshan B J** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms vaishnav b** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Akil A** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms avin v bangera** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms keerthan ch** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMAD** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms mohammed asad** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms mohammad** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Musthafa G** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms P.Shiva Ram** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms prajwal** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms rameej pm** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms shailesh.s** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms sreehari T** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Vichith** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Akash kana** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKHILA P M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Amoolya AR** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ARATHI** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Arvind Singh** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AYSHATHUL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Dravyaprabha.V** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms imzam k.a** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Jevian Loy** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms K SIDHARTH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **MAHSHOOQUE** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohammed Anas** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms mohammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohamed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Nandini M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms prajwal** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms prakyathji kotian** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sandhya** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sarishma.v** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms sayyed rizwan** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Shabaaz** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Chandan** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017 - 18**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK H M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ADITHYA C** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AMBRAS** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ANUSHREE R** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ASHITH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ASHISH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms DHANYA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms FATHIMA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KARTHIK R** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms KHADER** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms LARISA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MUHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOOSA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms PAWAN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms PISAVADIYA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms POORNASHRE** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms PRATHAM** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms RAAM KUMAR** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RAJA KUMAR** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RAJITH V K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms RAZIN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SACHIN M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SANDHRAM** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHREYA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms UCHIL NINAD** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms UMAQEEL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHREERAJESH** of IBCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHITHIN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms PRATHEEK P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABDUL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms A MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKSHAY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ALDRIN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms DAKSHAYANI** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms DHANUSH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms FAKRUDDIN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms JAYA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MUCHALLI** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMAD** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms NITHEESH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms REGO** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018 - 19**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABDUL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABDUL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABHIRAM** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABHISHEK** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABHISHEK** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ADARSH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ADHEENA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AFDHAL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ALEEMA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ANUPAMP** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms CHIRAG** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms FLOSSY J** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms G JEEVITHA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms GLERAN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms GOWDA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **HRIDHYA K P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms HRITHIK** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms IBRAHIM** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms KAJOL BEKAL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms KEERTHI.P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KRISHNAPRIY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOIDEEN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MUHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MULTAZAM** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2019 - 20**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms A.m. Rushaid** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Aditya** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Ahammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Althaf Khan** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms G Yadulal** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Georgin Shaju** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Harshitha** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Kiran Naik S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohamed Sahel** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohamed Zerin** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Muhamed Nihal** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Muhammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Nadheer Abdu** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sharoon Joseph** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Shetty Nimesh** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sree Hari** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Subodh. S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Vineesh Viswan** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Vinil Sumith** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abdu Razick** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abdul Hakeem** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abdul Jumail** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abdul Kidas** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abdul Lissan M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abdul Rahiman** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abhay Nagaraj** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Abhishek** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Adarsh C Naik** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Adarsh Manikoth** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Ahammad Sufail** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Ahammed Rifai** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Akshith A** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Ameer Ahmad** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Arya B M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Ashfaq Ashraf** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Asrid Ibrahim** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Bhuvanesh N** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms C K Ajith** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Deeksha** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Deekshith C S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Dennis Johnson** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Dhanush** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Divya Kumari H** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Falhurrahman** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Fouzan Soudagar** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Fuwhad** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Gayathri N K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Girish Kumar.c.h** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Gowri Murali** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Gurunandan G R** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Jaden Cedric** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Janith Sujathan** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Jaseel C H** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Jeevan Bhandary** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms K Anwesh Jain** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Kavan Kumar S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Kavya T** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Krishna Raj** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Lahari** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Lakshith P C** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mandira K N** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Manish** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Manvitha** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohammad Ijas** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohammed Akif** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mahammed Anas** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Mohammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Muhammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Muhammed** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Nikhil Kumar** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Nisha R** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Nishith** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Punith Kumar M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Saad Shaied** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sagar H R** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sandesh H P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms Sanjana** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2020-21**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms A GOUTHAM** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABDUL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-23**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAZIQ** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-24**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABHAY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-25**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABHIJITH K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-26**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABHIJITH M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-27**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABHINAV** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-28**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM K M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-29**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-30**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ABIN R C** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-31**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ADHISH M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-32**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AISWARYAN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-33**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKASH C P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-34**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKASH S S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-35**

Vice Chancellor
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKASH V** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-36**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKBARSHA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-37**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKHIL C** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-38**

Vice Chancellor
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKHILRAJ V P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-39**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AKHIL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-20**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **AKSHAY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-21**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ALFEEN** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-42**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AMAL T** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-43**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **AMISH V** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ANJITHA K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-45**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ANUAY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-46**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ANUSREE** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ARJUNES** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-48**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ARJUN MANOJ** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-49**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ASWANTH B B** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-50**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ASWIN A T** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-51**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms AYISHA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms BRINO PAUL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-53**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms DARSHANT** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-54**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms DEEPIKA R** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-55**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms DHANUSH G** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-56**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **GOPIKA SUNIL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms GOUDHAM** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-58**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms JAVAD** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-59**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms JISHNU** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-60**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KARTHIK P K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-61**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms KIRAN P K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-62**

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KIRAN RAJEEV** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-63**

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INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KRISHNAN S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-64**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-65**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-66**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-67**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MUFEEED M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-68**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MUHAMMAD** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-69**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MUHAMMAD** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-70**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-21**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-72**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-73**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-74**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-75**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **NANDAKISHOR** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-76**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms NANDANA M V** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms NANDHANA P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-78**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **NAVANEETH V** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-79**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms NEHA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-80**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms NIVEDH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-21**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms PANVITHA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-82**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms PARTHIV** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-83**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms PRANAV M** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-84**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RACHANA T** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-85**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RAHUL K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-86**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RANJANA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-87**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RENJITHA R** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-88**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RETHUBHEDH** of IBCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-89**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms RIDVED K V** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-20**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ROHIT K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-21**

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms S VIJITH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-92**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SANJAY P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-93**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SANJAY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-24**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SANJU ANAND** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-95**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHAZIYA A S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-96**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SIBIN BABY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-22**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SNEHA S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-98**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SNEHAL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-99**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SONA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-100**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SREEHARI K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-101**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SREEKANTHS** of IBCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-102**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SREEKUMARA** of IBCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-103**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SREERAG K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-104**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms SREYAS K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-105**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms TITO RETTY** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-106**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms THRISHA B S** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-107**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms VAISHNAV C K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-108**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms VAISHNAVI** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-109**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms VIGNESH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-110**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms VIJESH** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-111**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
Institute of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Dean
ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **VISHNU LAL K** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-112**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **VISHNU** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-113**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms VISHNU P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-114**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms VISHNU P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-115**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms VISMAYA** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-116**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ASWIN K P** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-117**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

DEAN
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Mangaluru - 575 001

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ICIS, SU Mangalore

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
Karnataka, Mangalore- 575001

Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms MOHAMMED** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-118**

Vice Chancellor
ICIS, SU Mangalore

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Mangaluru - 575 001

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Hardware and networking** course is awarded to **Mr/Ms ABDUL** of **IBCA** for the successful completion of the course during the year **2021-119**

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